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Severe Housing Deprivation in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2021

It decreased on average by 24.94%

Istat calculates the serious housing deprivation. The variable is defined as the percentage of people who live in overcrowded homes and who present at least one of the following three problems: a) structural problems of the home (ceilings, fixtures, etc.), b) not having a bathroom/shower with water current; c) brightness problems. The data refers to the period between 2004 and 2021 for the Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of severe housing deprivation in 2021. Valle d'Aosta is in first place by value of severe housing deprivation in 2021 with a value of 11.7%, followed by Molise with 11.6%, and 'Abruzzo with a value of 10.3%. In the middle of the table is Sicily with a value of 6.7%, followed by Umbria and Sardinia with a value of 5.9%. Veneto closes the ranking with a value of 4.3%, followed by Emilia Romagna with a value of 3% and Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of 2.3%.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in severe material deprivation between 2004 and 2021. Piedmont is in first place for the value of the percentage change in severe housing deprivation between with a value equal to 36.11% corresponding to a change from an amount from 7.2% in 2004 up to 9.8% in 2021 with a variation of 2.60 units. Valle d'Aosta follows with a variation of 67.44%, going from an amount of 7.00% in 2004 to a value of 11.7% in 2021 with a variation of 4.70 units. Liguria is in third place with a variation of 59.26% corresponding to a variation from 5.4% in 2004 up to 8.6% in 2021. In the middle of the table is Emilia Romagna with a variation of - 53.13% corresponding to a variation from 6.4% in 2004 up to a value of 3% in 2021 corresponding to a variation of -3.40%. Tuscany follows with a variation equal to 17.78% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.5% in 2004 up to a value of 5.3% in 2020 or a variation equal to an amount of 0.80 units. Umbria follows with a variation equal to -13.24% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.8% in 2004 up to a value of 5.9% in 2021 or equal to a variation of -0.90 unit. Calabria closes the ranking with a variation of -68.75% equal to a variation from an amount of 14.4 units in 2004 up to a value of 4.5% in 2021 or corresponding to a variation of -9.90 unit. Sicily follows with a variation equal to an amount of -55.33% corresponding to a variation from 15% in 2004 up to 6.7% in 2021 or a variation equal to -8.30 units. In last place is Sardinia with a variation equal to -42.16% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 10.2% up to a value of 5.9%. On average, the value of severe housing deprivation in the Italian regions decreased by 24.94%, going from an amount of 6.59% in 2004 to a value of 8.78% in 2021.

Severe housing deprivation in the Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021. Severe housing deprivation in Northern Italy decreased by 11.86%, going from a value of 5.9% in 2004 to 5.2% in 2021. Severe housing deprivation in the North West increased by 10.71% between 2004 and 2021, going from a value of 5.6% to 6.2%. Severe housing deprivation in the North-East decreased by - 41.27% corresponding to an amount of 6.3% in 2004 up to 3.7% in 2021. Severe housing deprivation

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in Central Italy decreased by 12.33% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 7.3% in 2004 up to 6.4% in 2021. Severe housing deprivation in the South decreased by 50.38% going from an amount of 13.1% in 2004 up to 6.5% in 2021. Severe housing deprivation in Southern Italy decreased by 50.00%, going from an amount of 12.8% in 2004 to 6.4% in 2021. Severe housing deprivation in the Islands decreased by 52.90% going from an amount of 13.8% in 2004 up to 6.5% in 2021.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Campania, Sicily, Calabria, Basilicata, Abruzzo, Lazio, Sardinia, Molise;
- Cluster 2: Tuscany, Veneto, Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Liguria, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Piedmont, Valle d'Aosta, Trentino Alto Adige, Umbria, Puglia, Marche.

Considering the value of the average of the clusters we can see that Cluster 1 is dominant compared to Cluster 2, i.e.: $C1 > C2$. We can note that cluster 1 essentially consists of the southern regions with the exception of Lazio. On the contrary, Puglia is the only southern region to be present in cluster 2, i.e. the cluster that presents more moderate levels of severe housing deprivation.

Conclusions. Severe housing deprivation in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2021 decreased on average in the Italian regions by an amount equal to -24.94%. We can note that there has been a great convergence in the value of severe housing deprivation in the southern regions compared to the central-northern regions. However, severe housing deprivation in the North-East has much lower levels than in the other Italian macro-regions with a value of 3.7%. If we consider the Italian data we can note that approximately 5.9% of the Italian population suffers from severe housing deprivation. That is, considering that the Italian population is approximately 59 million inhabitants, it follows that approximately 3.5 million Italians experience conditions of severe housing deprivation.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

